

Should my chatbot be register-specific?: Register Analysis in the Context of Tourism Interactions

1 Overall Register Analysis: Statistical Results

Register Analysis (FLG vs. DailyDialog, DSTC, and Frames datasets): Table 1 shows the results of the perMANOVA analysis where the five dimensions of register are the dependent variable and the corpora are the independent variable. The result shows that there is a difference among the corpora, and the difference is observable across all dimensions, according to the univariate analysis results. Table 2 shows the contrasts among corpora. All the corpora are significantly different from each other, except for DSTC and FLG, considering a model with all the corpora as independent variable.

Table 1: PERMANOVA: dimension scores per corpus and univariate analysis of dimension scores

PERMANOVA	Df	F-value	p-value
Corpora	3	134.75	1.00E-04
Response dim_1			
	Df	F-value	p-value
Corpora	3	135.15	2.20E-16
Response dim_2			
	Df	F-value	p-value
Corpora	3	105.86	2.20E-16
Response dim_3			
	Df	F-value	p-value
Corpora	3	167.03	2.20E-16
Response dim_4			
	Df	F-value	p-value
Corpora	3	152.24	2.20E-16
Response dim_5			
	Df	F-value	p-value
Corpora	3	57.442	2.20E-16

Table 2: MANOVA contrasts

MANOVA contrasts			
	FLG	DailyDialog	Frames
DailyDialog	<.0001		
Frames	0.0017	<.0001	
DSTC	0.8169	<.0001	<.0001

Tables 3 through 7 summarize the analysis of the individual features for each dimension. The green background for a cell represents that the value of the estimate is greater than the estimated for the intercept (FLG). In the p-value columns, the color red represents p-value significant at 0.05 significance level while an orange background represents significance at 0.10 significance level. Features in parenthesis have negative impact in the dimension score.

Table 3: Individual features analysis for Dimension 1

Dimension 1	Estimate				F	p-value
	FLG	DSTC	Frames	DailyDialog		
Private verbs	6.32	0.57	4.37	14.70	181.50	0.00
That deletion	0.55	0.89	1.03	4.79	63.39	0.00
Contractions	8.61	6.51	6.61	26.68	206.30	0.00
Present verbs	121.92	124.89	126.00	159.17	184.10	0.00
Second person pronouns	36.59	51.05	52.50	81.76	222.20	0.00
Do as a pro-verb	1.99	0.00	2.45	5.72	51.62	0.00
Demonstrative pronouns	2.94	4.02	4.02	6.22	11.04	0.00
Emphatics	6.49	0.00	1.61	7.23	105.00	0.00
First person pronouns	15.78	18.72	37.13	55.13	306.60	0.00
Pronoun "it"	11.93	1.52	8.67	17.45	141.50	0.00
Be as main verb	4.25	0.00	4.27	4.35	65.61	0.00
Causative subordination	0.52	0.00	0.03	0.20	12.77	0.00
Discourse particles	1.44	0.36	3.30	6.29	64.64	0.00
Indefinite pronouns	3.02	2.43	5.43	7.57	32.51	0.00
General hedges	0.09	0.00	0.07	0.55	11.00	0.00
Amplifiers	2.21	0.00	0.92	2.15	35.99	0.00
WH questions	3.59	10.66	6.19	5.83	53.01	0.00
Possibility modals	14.55	27.00	11.45	17.72	169.50	0.00
Non-phrasal coordination	10.28	1.42	8.20	6.55	105.50	0.00
WH clauses	0.35	0.00	0.37	0.46	5.29	0.00
Final preposition	2.40	0.00	3.95	1.50	78.90	0.00
(Nouns)	300.83	354.48	266.43	225.61	709.90	0.00
(Prepositions)	100.89	93.52	108.23	70.60	214.40	0.00
(Attributive adjectives)	47.76	46.47	23.01	19.49	325.50	0.00
(Type/Token ratio)	14.11	14.67	16.12	8.53	404.80	0.00
(Word length)	4.35	4.36	4.14	3.97	296.20	0.00

Table 4: Individual features analysis for Dimension 2

Dimension 2	Estimate				F	p-value
	FLG	DSTC	Frames	DailyDialog		
Past tense verbs	7.94	0.86	3.87	8.57	84.87	0.00
Third person pronouns	10.74	0.03	1.07	4.00	99.29	0.00
Perfect aspects verbs	1.38	0.00	2.17	3.48	47.18	0.00
Public verbs	1.01	1.10	1.09	2.71	18.01	0.00

Table 5: Individual features analysis for Dimension 3

Dimension 3	Estimate				F	p-value
	FLG	DSTC	Frames	DailyDialog		
WH relative clauses on object positions	0.08	0.00	0.16	0.12	2.08	0.10
Pied piping constructions	0.09	0.00	0.12	0.19	1.91	0.13
WH relative clauses on subject positions	1.22	0.06	0.61	0.21	25.86	0.00
Phrasal coordination	0.93	0.00	0.31	1.11	15.12	0.00
Nominalizations	28.20	57.35	38.08	20.98	380.30	0.00
(Time adverbials)	2.43	0.00	2.71	7.47	108.60	0.00
(Place adverbials)	13.48	13.40	10.57	17.92	29.60	0.00
(Adverbs)	35.69	9.75	24.80	36.33	198.00	0.00

Table 6: Individual features analysis for Dimension 4

Dimension 4	Estimate				F	p-value
	FLG	DSTC	Frames	DailyDialog		
Infinitives	7.21	0.08	10.55	9.23	185.00	0.00
Prediction modals	11.01	9.69	20.98	21.84	110.70	0.00
Suasive verbs	2.88	0.00	0.84	0.56	41.81	0.00
Conditional subordination	5.61	0.28	1.46	2.47	57.00	0.00
Necessity modals	1.57	0.00	0.58	4.18	77.30	0.00
Split auxiliaries	2.76	1.94	0.79	1.36	17.67	0.00

Table 7: Individual features analysis for Dimension 5

Dimension 5	Estimate				F	p-value
	FLG	DSTC	Frames	DailyDialog		
Conjunctions	1.56	1.30	3.46	5.22	36.33	0.00
Agentless passives	5.01	0.14	2.51	3.06	56.99	0.00
Past participial clauses	9.83	10.81	3.33	7.21	82.97	0.00
BY-passives	0.19	0.00	0.08	0.06	2.36	0.07
Other adverbial subordinators	2.20	0.06	1.60	3.40	49.79	0.00

Tables 8 through 11 summarize the linguistic features that characterize the register of tourist assistants regarding each register dimension. The label “Consistently present” (in green) are the linguistic features that appear in more than 75% of the texts; “Consistently absent” (in red) are the features that are absent in more than 75% of the texts; and “No clear tendency” (in yellow) are the features neither present nor absent (the counts are equal to 0.0 for 25-75% of the data). Features in parenthesis have a negative impact on the dimension score.

Table 8: Linguistic features for Dimension 1 per corpora

Dimension 1	Corpora			
	FLG	DSTC	Frames	DailyDialog
Private verbs	No clear tendency	Consistently absent	No clear tendency	No clear tendency
That deletion	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent
Contractions	No clear tendency	No clear tendency	No clear tendency	No clear tendency
Present verbs	Consistently present	Consistently present	Consistently present	Consistently present
Second-person pronouns	Consistently present	Consistently present	Consistently present	Consistently present
Do as a pro-verb	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent
Demonstrative pronouns	Consistently absent	No clear tendency	No clear tendency	Consistently absent
Emphatics	No clear tendency	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent
First-person pronouns	No clear tendency	Consistently present	Consistently present	Consistently present
Pronoun “it”	No clear tendency	Consistently absent	No clear tendency	No clear tendency
Be as main verb	No clear tendency	Consistently absent	No clear tendency	Consistently absent
Causative subordination	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent
Discourse particles	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent
Indefinite pronouns	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	No clear tendency	Consistently absent
General hedges	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent
Amplifiers	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent
WH questions	Consistently absent	Consistently present	No clear tendency	Consistently absent
Possibility modals	No clear tendency	Consistently present	No clear tendency	No clear tendency
Non-phrasal coordination	No clear tendency	Consistently absent	No clear tendency	Consistently absent
WH clauses	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent
Final preposition	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	No clear tendency	Consistently absent
(Nouns)	Consistently present	Consistently present	Consistently present	Consistently present
(Prepositions)	present	Consistently present	Consistently present	Consistently present
(Attributive adjectives)	Consistently present	Consistently present	Consistently present	No clear tendency

Table 9: Linguistic features for Dimension 2 and Dimension 3 per corpora

Dimension 2	Corpora			
	FLG	DSTC	Frames	DailyDialog
Past tense verbs	No clear tendency	Consistently absent	No clear tendency	Consistently absent
Third person pronouns	No clear tendency	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent
Perfect aspects verbs	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent
Public verbs	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent
Dimension 3	Corpora			
	FLG	DSTC	Frames	DailyDialog
WH relative clauses on object positions	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent
Pied piping constructions	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent
WH relative clauses on subject positions	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent
Phrasal coordination	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent
Nominalizations	No clear tendency	Consistently present	Consistently present	No clear tendency
(Time adverbials)	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent
(Place adverbials)	No clear tendency	No clear tendency	No clear tendency	No clear tendency
(Adverbs)	Consistently present	No clear tendency	Consistently present	No clear tendency

Table 10: Linguistic features for Dimension 4 per corpora

Dimension 4	Corpora			
	FLG	DSTC	Frames	DailyDialog
Infinitives	No clear tendency	Consistently absent	No clear tendency	No clear tendency
Prediction modals	No clear tendency	No clear tendency	Consistently present	No clear tendency
Suasive verbs	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent
Conditional subordination	No clear tendency	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent
Necessity modals	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent
Split auxiliaries	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent

Table 11: Linguistic features for Dimension 5 per corpora

Dimension 5	Corpora			
	FLG	DSTC	Frames	DailyDialog
Conjunctions	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent
Agentless passives	No clear tendency	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent
Past participial clauses	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent
BY-passives	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent
Other adverbial subordinators	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent	Consistently absent